

When Planets Breathe: Models Constrain the Circumstances for Detection of Biomarker Gases on the Terrestrial Exoplanets of M Dwarfs

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Abstract

When it comes to worlds beyond our solar system, we rely on methods of remote observation to search for evidence of extraterrestrial life. One such method is transmission spectroscopy, which looks at the fraction of starlight transmitted through the gaseous envelope or atmosphere of an exoplanet during primary transit. Many of Earth's atmospheric components are biogenic in origin. If we can observe a similar suite of biomarker gases in the atmosphere of an exoplanet, we may confirm an unambiguous detection of life on another world. In this paper, I present theoretical calculations which place constraints on the detection of information-rich biomarkers, with a specific focus on O₂. I use PHOENIX stellar spectra for stars with the characteristic size and temperature of M dwarfs of approximately 0.2-0.5M_⊙ (Husser et al. 2013), and the absorption spectra of O₂ in an Earth-like atmosphere, calculated by Rodler & López-Morales (2014), to simulate the transmission spectrum of an O₂-rich Earth-like exoplanet as observed from an Earth-based telescope. By simulating these observations with different values of instrumental resolution and the planet's distance from Earth, I discovered that O₂ features are resolvable at resolutions R=10000 to 100000 for star systems at distances out to 10 pc, for a star of radius 0.2 solar radii. Beyond about 10 pc, O₂ absorption features are irretrievable with a 39.5-meter telescope, the largest yet under construction. O₂ absorption features are also irretrievable for stars larger than 0.5 solar radii even at distances of 10 pc or less. With my models, these constraints can be recalculated for the absorption features of more explicit biomarkers fairly easily by inputting absorption spectra from the HITRAN database for these molecules, which I attempted with deuterated water (Rothman et al. 2013).

1.0 Introduction/Background

Earth's past, present, and future can be discussed in terms of two spheres: the physical world and the biological world. The physical world involves, among other things, geophysics, climate, ocean chemistry, and all of the intricate feedback systems that connect them. The biological world includes everything related to life and its persistence, e.g. photosynthesis and metabolism. The physical and the biological world are inextricably linked, with the physical world providing the conditions that constrain how the biological world may develop, and life producing effects on the physical world that may reshape the Earth drastically. One of the best examples of this interplay is the great oxygenation event at 2.3 Ga. Photosynthetic organisms liberated molecular oxygen through their production of organic material, gradually oxygenating the oceans and leading to the accumulation of oxygen in the atmosphere (Holland 2002). In addition to having huge implications for the evolution of more energetically favorable metabolisms, and more complex life forms, the oxygenation of Earth's atmosphere also led to significant changes in surface chemistry and climate, through the production of UV-absorbent ozone or O₃. This makes oxygen an important biomarker gas – an atmospheric indicator of life on the surface of our planet.

There are, however, abiogenic processes that produce atmospheric oxygen, including the photodissociation of water, so the detection of atmospheric O₂ may not provide definitive evidence of life on its own (Wordsworth & Pierrehumbert 2014). Photodissociation of water generates O₂ without the aid of biology, producing a certain mass-independent isotope effect on atmospheric water vapor. If the ratio of isotopically heavy to light water does not reveal this isotope effect, but O₂ and O₃ are

detected at significant abundances, it might confirm the biogenic origins of molecular oxygen on that planet.

If we could observe other biomarker gases, in addition to oxygen, we might draw ever more interesting conclusions. Methane (CH_4) is one such biomarker gas, generated by methanogenic archaea and industrial agriculture. Methane is quickly oxidized in Earth's atmosphere, in the presence of O_2 and O_3 , so its sustained abundance in the atmosphere speaks to the continual production of the gas by active biological processes. So the presence of methane and molecular oxygen in Earth's atmosphere might also constitute a definitive detection of life.

Of course, the point is not to characterize the footprint of biology upon the Earth's atmosphere. Living here ourselves, we already know a great deal about the impact of life on the environment. What we are truly interested in is observing the footprint of biology upon the atmosphere of an Earth-like exoplanet – i.e. searching for life elsewhere in the universe using remote observing techniques. To observe an exoplanet atmosphere, we must utilize transmission spectroscopy of relatively dim starlight through the atmosphere of a transiting, terrestrial planet (Charbonneau & Deming 2007). As the planet passes in front of its star, it blocks a fraction of the star's light – but a small fraction of light passes through the “annulus” of the planet's atmospheric veneer. Molecular components of that atmosphere absorb the light of the star at telltale wavelengths. The comparison of the star's spectrum during and after the planet's primary transit can reveal the spectral absorption features that point to the atmospheric composition of the planet.

Transmission spectroscopy was proposed as a method for the study of exoplanet atmospheres almost fifteen years ago, and has been used to study the compositions of large, gaseous exoplanets, but it has yet to be applied for terrestrial worlds (Seager & Sasselov 2000). In this paper, I present the results of modeling routines which simulate the transmission of light from an average M dwarf star through the atmospheres of hypothetical Earth-like planets with biomarker-rich atmospheres and minimal clouds. These routines follow the light from star, to planet, across space, through the Earth's atmosphere, and into large Earth-based telescopes – to constrain the circumstances under which the detection of any incriminating biomarkers could be possible. In this paper, I focus on O_2 as my primary biomarker of interest.

2.0 Methods

Table of Parameters

Symbol	Meaning	Value
R_*	stellar radius	0.2-1 R_\odot or 695500 km
R	resolution	1000-100000
a	telescope mirror size	3950 cm or 39.5 m
D	distance between Earth and star system	1-20 pc
t	integration time	7200 s or 2 h
r	planet radius	1 r_{Earth} or 6378 km
v	planet velocity, with respect to Earth	0-20 km/s
s	scale height of planetary atmosphere	8 km
e	efficiency	0.2
λ	wavelength of interest	depends on molecule
$\Delta\lambda$	range of wavelengths	depends on molecule

2.1 The Star

As discussed in previous literature, it is easier to observe small, terrestrial planets transiting smaller stars because a greater fraction of the light is obscured than if the same planets transited a larger star (Charbonneau & Deming 2007). This means that absorption features will appear stronger with respect to the stellar spectrum. Additionally, stars smaller and cooler than our own sun are much more common than sun-like stars within the neighborhood of about 10 pc (Henry et al. 2006). So statistically, we would expect our best and terrestrial candidates for transmission spectroscopy to orbit smaller, cooler stars, i.e. M dwarfs (Dressing and Charbonneau 2013).

For my purposes, I used the PHOENIX Stellar Models to generate the spectrum of an M dwarf star (Husser et al. 2013). My star's temperature = 3800 K, and I varied its radius between 0.2 and 1 R_{\odot} to investigate the effects of stellar size on biomarker detections. In reality, temperature and size will scale together, but for our purposes we maintain a certain temperature regardless of size. The temperature is a parameter used to generate the spectrum, but the intensity of that spectrum is scaled by the star size, which I set in my own models.

Figure 1. On the left, the model emission spectrum for an M-dwarf star of temperature 3800 K and radius $0.2R_{\odot}$ from the PHOENIX library is shown (Husser et al. 2013). The PHOENIX library generates spectra in units of energy per wavelength per area per time, which my model converts to photons per wavelength, integrated over area and here labeled as “photon flux” in the sense that photos are striking a detector surface. On the right, select absorption features for the O_2 molecule within the 760 nm waveband are shown (Rodler & López-Morales 2013).

My models store the stellar spectrum in two arrays – one for the flux of photons from the star's surface, integrated over area, and one for the wavelength grid they are plotted against.

2.2 The Planetary Atmosphere

Once light leaves the stellar surface, it begins its journey toward our telescopes. It passes first through the atmosphere of its transiting, terrestrial exoplanet. For my purposes, this atmosphere is simplified to a single component in my most basic models: O_2 gas at Earth-like abundances. O_2 has several different absorption features, but I use a combination of bands from Earth models constructed by Florian Rodler and Mercedes López-Morales and detailed in their paper (2014). These bands, like my stellar spectrum, are stored in two arrays – one for the wavelength grid, and one for absorption values between 0 and 1, indicating the depth of each line. These depths are scaled by the size of the planet's

atmosphere; no light will pass through the disk of the rock planet itself, so the absorption is multiplied by the geometry of the atmospheric veneer, which extends beyond the planet’s radius by many kilometers. On Earth, the density of our atmosphere falls off (for most gases) by a factor of $e = 2.71828$ with each “scale height,” which has an 8 km thickness. I applied the same geometric scaling to my absorption features, assuming a total atmospheric size of 5 scale heights.

Because the absorption features have been calculated from different models than the stellar spectrum, they are aligned on a different wavelength grid. My program interpolates the absorption values onto the wavelength grid of the stellar spectrum, before multiplying them by the stellar spectrum.

2.3 Attenuation across Space

After the starlight passes through the planetary atmosphere, it must travel across mostly empty space before reaching the observer on Earth. Much light is lost across that distance, as it is emitted in all directions, and – at greater distances – the density of emission lines becomes lower and lower. This phenomenon is captured by the inverse square law, which dictates how light is attenuated by the inverse square of distance. I multiply my spectrum (which now contains information from both stellar emissions and absorptions in the stellar and planetary atmospheres) by the inverse square of the distance between Earth and the model star. This distance is a parameter in my models that can be set to investigate the limits of observations. The default distance is 1 pc.

2.4 The Telluric Atmosphere

Once the planet-imprinted spectrum travels through space, the last obstacle it faces – before it can be measured – is the telluric or Earthly atmosphere. If we are interested in interpreting the absorption features of a distant Earth-like atmosphere, then the presence of another Earth-like atmosphere so *conspicuously* in the foreground is important to account for. In my models, the distant exoplanet of interest and the Earth have the same oxygen absorption features, but the Earth’s features are many times stronger than the exoplanet’s – lacking the attenuation due to the geometry of transmission through an atmospheric annulus. Similarly to the planetary atmosphere, I multiply Earth’s absorption features by the stellar spectrum after interpolating said features onto a like wavelength grid. Because the exoplanet’s atmospheric signature is so weak, relative to the signal of the telluric atmosphere, the stellar spectrum during the exoplanet’s transit appears almost identical to the stellar spectrum after the transit.

Figure 2. Stellar spectra with O₂ absorption features from both telluric and exoplanet atmospheres

superimposed. The plot at left contains only the O₂ from the telluric atmosphere. The plot at right contains the O₂ features from both the exoplanet and telluric atmospheres. R = 10000.

Other light lost on the journey through the telluric atmosphere and instrumental detectors is accounted for by an “efficiency” factor 0.2, which is also multiplied by the spectrum.

2.5 Telescopes and Noise

Earth-based telescopes need to collect as many photons as possible to increase the level of spectral detail and boost the signal to noise ratio for all detections; this is accomplished by increasing the size of the telescope mirror and/or maximizing integration time over the course of a transit, both of which are parameters in my models. Telescope size is held at a mirror diameter of 39.5 meters (the anticipated size of the European Extremely Large Telescope E-ELT, one of a promising next-generation of large, Earth-based telescopes that will contribute to the detailed characterization of exoplanets and the search for life. This group includes the E-ELT, the Giant Magellan Telescope GMT, and the Thirty Meter Telescope TMT.) Integration time is held at 2 hours, the approximate transit duration for an Earth-like planet across the disk of an average M dwarf star (Winn 2011). But there are also many sources of noise on the pathway from stellar surface to the detector, including background radiation and instrumental fluctuations. The actual number of photons gathered at each wavelength is also critical – the fewer the photons, the larger the noise factored into each bin.

In my models, I consolidate all of these sources of noise into a single calculation. The noise at each wavelength bin is a random value selected from a normal distribution with a mean of zero and a standard deviation equal to the square root of the photon count in the given bin. The normal distribution represents the convergence of the Poisson noise to a normal distribution at large photon values. Noise is calculated for both the stellar + planetary + telluric spectrum and the stellar + telluric spectrum and added to each (figure 3).

Figure 3. Stellar spectra with O₂ absorption features from both telluric and exoplanet atmospheres superimposed, with the addition of noise. The plot at left contains only the O₂ from the telluric atmosphere. The plot at right contains the O₂ features from both the exoplanet and telluric atmospheres. R = 10000. Note that the noise is low enough that the plots look almost identical to those in Figure 2.

2.6 Correcting for Saturation

O₂ and H₂O features from the O₂ and H₂O-rich telluric atmosphere may saturate, blocking out all photon signal at particular wavelengths. With extremely low or no signal, noise becomes quite large,

and a few noisy wavelengths can confound our observations. My model handles this by “masking” saturated wavelengths with values from the stellar spectrum without the telluric absorptions. Absorptions from the planetary atmosphere will always be too small to have the same effect, and therefore do not require masking.

Saturation will not be an issue for molecules other than H₂O and O₂ in the optical waveband, since these are the only molecules with both optical transitions and telluric abundances high enough to obliterate the signal.

2.7 Binning

When attempting to resolve information-rich spectral features, improving the ratio of actual signal to incident noise is extremely important. When a spectrum is un-binned, every pixel in the wavelength grid contains the photon count for that wavelength plus or minus a value representing noise. Every pixel is noisy. When a spectrum is binned, multiple pixels are combined, adding the photons up for a larger “signal” and reducing the noise to a single intrinsic noise value. Every value in the binned spectrum therefore has greater certainty. The size of the bins is determined by the spectral resolution of our telescope’s light-gathering instruments. Qualitatively, higher resolution corresponds to smaller bins and finer spectral detail:

R = resolution, with R typically varying between 10,000 and 100,000 for the most powerful telescopes.

λ = wavelength of interest, centered on an important molecular transition/absorption band

$\Delta\lambda = \lambda/R$ = size of each wavelength bin

My models divide the wavelength range surrounding the molecular absorption band of interest into bins of size $\Delta\lambda$. Photons at wavelengths within each bin are summed, divided by the number of wavelengths in the grid actually encapsulated by the boundaries of the bin, and multiplied by $\Delta\lambda$. This is done for both the stellar + planetary + telluric spectrum and the stellar + telluric spectrum, concurrently with interpolation onto a revised wavelength grid.

2.8 Cancelling the Telluric Atmosphere

To eliminate the dominant telluric features from the spectra, I take the ratio of these spectra: the noisy stellar + planetary + telluric spectrum and the stellar + telluric spectrum. In the ratio spectrum, only the planetary atmosphere plus noise remains.

Figure 4. Ratio of the stellar + planetary + telluric + noise spectrum to the stellar + telluric + noise spectrum. Note how the O₂ feature from the planetary spectrum is now visible. $R = 10000$, $D = 1$ pc, $r = 0.2 \cdot R_{\oplus}$.

2.9 Doppler Shift and Cross Correlation

The planetary system that we would observe at distance is moving relative to the observer on Earth – by tens of kilometers per second. This means the absorption features in the atmosphere of an exoplanet will be Doppler-shifted by a certain number of pixels, according to the spectral resolution of the telescope, relative to the positions of the same features in the telluric atmosphere. The velocity of the planetary system relative to Earth is a parameter in my models, and alters the wavelength positions of absorption features.

For systems where the velocity shifts the feature by more than a few pixels, taking the ratio of the stellar + planetary + telluric spectrum and the stellar + telluric spectrum may reveal the absorption features at wavelengths uncharacteristic of the molecule of interest. This is particularly true at low resolutions where individual pixels contain information for a greater range of wavelengths. When I take the ratio, the signal may appear buried in noise, despite high resolutions or long integration times. I cannot always identify the signal visually. But mathematically, there is a way to ascertain the features' identity: cross correlation of the spectral ratio with a standard containing the absorption feature alone.

Cross correlation calculates the sum of the products of all overlapping values in two given lists of data, as the lists are “shifted” over each other, such that different values overlap with each shift. The maximum sum of products will occur for the “shift” at which the absorption features align most perfectly. That shift is related to the velocity of the planetary system. My routines perform a normalized cross correlation on the spectral ratio and an “absorption standard” containing the absorption feature without the effects of Doppler shift. Because the sum of the products of shifted arrays will leave values at the ends of arrays without a complement, cross correlation calculations can be distorted by what we call “edge effects,” where the peak correlation value reflects the obvious fact that correlation falls off as the edges overlap less. Ideally, we are interested in a more information-rich cross correlation peak that reflects the overlapping of the absorption features, and the velocity at which the overlap occurs. My models handle edge effects “wrapping.” This means that as the “shift” of the cross correlation routine moves the edges of the arrays more out of line with one another, the hanging

values are “wrapped” around to be multiplied with corresponding values at the beginning of the array. The result is a cross correlation peak that truly represents the velocity shift (figure 5).

Figure 5. The left plot shows a close-up on the peak of the cross correlation function for the spectral ratio and absorption features shown above in Figures 5 and 2, respectively. The right plot shows the spectral ratio with noise, just as in figure 4. $R = 10000$, $R = 10000$, $D = 1$ pc, $r = 0.2 \cdot R_{\oplus}$.

2.10 Determining Constraints

The primary purpose of these models was to find the range of parameter values within which the O_2 absorption feature at 760 nm from an exo-Earth atmosphere could be observed. The parameters tested included: instrumental resolution R , stellar size r , and distance between Earth and exoplanetary system D . The range of R values tested in figure 6 represents the range for which the O_2 absorption features are resolvable. The range of r values tested in figure 7 and the range of D values in figure 8 illustrate the points beyond which O_2 features are unresolvable. R values lower than 10000 were tested, but not shown here due to the low number of bins, which make the plots largely unreadable (on the order of 10^2 data points or less.)

2.11 $HD^{16}O$ Models

These models can be utilized for any absorption feature, importing absorption values from the HITRAN database (Rothman et al. 2013). Since cooler stars emit most strongly in the optical or near-infrared (figure 1), observers focus on molecules with transitions in these parts of the spectrum. Biologically interesting molecules in this range include O_2 and H_2O , of course, but also heavier isotopologues of water like $HD^{16}O$ and $D_2^{16}O$. As described in the introduction, precise measurements of heavy water abundances and light water abundances can be used to assess the isotope effect that accompanies the formation of O_2 . If O_2 is abiogenically produced by the high-energy irradiation of surface oceans, there could be a mass-independent effect distinct from the effect of oxygenic photosynthesis (Wordsworth & Pierrehumbert 2014). For this paper, I made a first attempt at resolving an $HD^{16}O$ absorption feature using the most favorable combination of parameters: $D = 1$ pc, $r = 0.2 R_{\oplus}$, and $R = 100000$. The result is shown in figure 9.

3.0 Results

Figure 6. These plots contain the calculated ratio of the stellar + planetary + telluric spectrum and the stellar + telluric spectrum, alongside the normalized cross correlation of that ratio with the un-shifted absorption spectrum for O_2 . $R = 10000, 50000, \text{ and } 100000$. At higher resolutions, more absorption lines are resolvable. For each plot, distance between telescope and star system = 1 pc, and star size is $0.2 R_{\odot}$.

Figure 7. These plots contain the calculated ratio of the stellar + planetary + telluric spectrum and the stellar + telluric spectrum, alongside the normalized cross correlation of that ratio with the un-shifted absorption spectrum for O_2 . Star size = $0.2 R_{\odot}$, $0.5 R_{\odot}$, and $1 R_{\odot}$. Larger stars obscure the signal from the planetary atmosphere, making it more difficult to resolve. In this way, my models further validate ongoing surveys of M dwarfs as candidates for finding life-bearing terrestrial exoplanets. For each plot, distance between telescope and star system = 1 pc, and $R = 100000$.

Figure 8. These plots contain the calculated ratio of the stellar + planetary + telluric spectrum and the stellar + telluric spectrum, alongside the normalized cross correlation of that ratio with the un-shifted absorption spectrum for O_2 . Distance = 1 pc, 10 pc, and 20 pc. At distance increases, the O_2 absorption bands become more difficult to resolve. For each plot, star size = $0.2 R_\odot$, and $R = 100000$.

Figure 9. These plots contain the calculated ratio of the stellar + planetary + telluric spectrum and the stellar + telluric spectrum, alongside the normalized cross correlation of that ratio with the un-shifted absorption spectrum for HD¹⁶O, an isotopologue of water. The detection and measurement of this absorption feature relative to H₂O features may be necessary to determine the biogenicity of atmospheric O₂ on a terrestrial exoplanet. Limits on the observation of this feature follow the same trends as those on O₂ features above, regarding the size of the star the exoplanet orbits, Earth's distance to said star, and the spectral resolution of the instruments of observation. For each plot, distance = 1 pc, star size = 0.2 R_⊙, and R = 100000. Note the weakness of the HDO feature, compared to O₂ even at comparable abundances. There are fewer photons from the star at these longer wavelengths (around 5300 nm), which results in larger relative noise which may bury the absorption feature.

4.0 Discussion

My models demonstrate that an observer's ability to resolve the absorption features of key biomarker gases via transmission spectroscopy is limited by interstellar distance, spectral resolution, and stellar type. As depicted in Figure 6 at $R \leq 10000$, Earth-like abundances of molecular oxygen (O₂) cannot be resolved in the atmospheric signatures of terrestrial exoplanets orbiting an average M dwarf star (3800 K, $R_* = 0.2R_{\odot}$) at distances greater than 10 pc. In Figure 7, it is also shown that for stars with radius $R_* \geq 0.5 R_{\odot}$ (50% size of the sun), all other parameters unchanged, Earth-like O₂ features are also undetectable. With these constraints taken into consideration, many candidate stars still remain whose terrestrial planets may have atmospheres amenable to this kind of spectral analysis. I base this on statistical surveys which show that 75% of the stars within 10 pc are M dwarfs, and of these 15% are orbited by Earth like planets at habitable-zone distances (Dressing & Charbonneau 2013). There are several hundred M dwarf stars within 10 pc (Henry et al. 2006), so about 40-50 are believed to host Earth-like exoplanets in their habitable zones. Of these, the likelihood of transit is only about 1/20, so only about 2 planets will be observable terrestrial exoplanets in the habitable zones of M dwarfs within 10 pc. My models have demonstrated that we would be able to definitively detect and measure key biomarkers O₂ (and potentially HDO) on all of these statistically-likely exoplanets, or at least O₂. 2 is a manageable number – we could potentially find them both in a survey of the nearest M dwarfs. But it is also a small number – if oxygenic photosynthesizers did not arise on any of these dozen worlds, we might not find any signal at all.

As earlier mentioned, the European Extremely Large Telescope is one of three large telescopes which will have the spectral resolution and light-collection ability to make observations of the sort exemplified in my models. E-ELT, the Giant Magellan Telescope, and the under-construction Thirty-Meter Telescope, to name a few, will all be able to resolve O₂ features and HDO features on that promising handful of terrestrial worlds.

5.0 Future Work

Going forward, we will use the models developed in this investigation to calculate the same constraints for observations of other biomarker gases and their isotopologues, starting with HD¹⁶O and D₂¹⁶O. But just as the isotopic fractionation of water and oxygen differs based on the biogenic or abiogenic mechanism of its formation, so too does the fractionation of other species indicate chemical and biological origins. Other molecular candidates under consideration are CH₄ and possibly SO₂ and H₂S. Atmospheric pools of methane may preserve physical and biological fractionation signals, and SO₂ and H₂S are sulfur species which participate in biological cycling on Earth and may carry signals of like processes on other planets.

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